

Response Paper

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COURSE CODE: ACA-401

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MS Word for Mac 2019

GUIDE TO ACADEMIC & PROFESSIONAL WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have started my master's degree program with EUCLID and had a chance to study the basics of academic writing in period one coursepack. In distance learning, academic writing provides the foremost criteria for judging students' eligibility. We the students do not have a chance to prove our eligibility by participating in class discussions. It is only possible through writings that we can communicate well with our instructors. It is like a mirror where Instructors can see the reflection of students. Thankfully, EUCLID's International Academic and Professional Paper Writing course gives its students a window of opportunity to enhance their writing skills. Going through the period one coursepack was just like getting ready for a long journey of academic self-elevation EUCLID provides to its students.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The course starts with the guidance tools required for essay writing. EUCLID provides a step by step guidance of essay writing. The primary step includes the proper planning and carrying a research about the topic. In order to be a good writer, it is imperative to be a good reader. Researching about the topic before writing always equip us with more information, better knowledge and helps in shaping up our ideas. EUCLID provided coursepack pays emphasis on the research work required for the essay. Even in my everyday life I cannot debate on any issue without conducting a proper research. After

research has been done and notes of the important points have been taken it is time to pen down the essay. Notes taking is another important requirement for a good piece of writing as it not only helps in memorizing the important points but also helps in the writing of an essay.

The essay written after thorough research should be coherent and able to grab the attention of the reader from the beginning till the end. Repetition of words and ideas loses the readers interest. Proper structure (introduction, arguments and conclusion) from the beginning till the end gives reader a clear idea about the topic. Once written it should be read several times in order to avoid mistakes. Stifling the essay after writing is always beneficial for the student. I have always found it helpful if a friend can have a look at my writing as a critic and guide me in making them better.

Giving the citation references wherever needed and citing the bibliography in the end helps completing the essay. They are indeed the most important part of writing an essay and therefore should be properly done.

Euclid University's repeated emphasis against plagiarism shows how much importance they give to the original work of the author. Plagiarism should be discouraged in all forums of writing.

3) REFERENCING

EUCLID provides two types of citations in its coursepack:

1. In-text citations includes the name(s) of the author and page number. It is always mentioned immediately after the quote. In text citation is different from bibliographical references because they appear along with the quote and includes the author name and page number showing where the information has come from
2. List of the work cited in the end of the essay as bibliography or references (EUCLID 2015, 33). Footnotes at the end of the essay and the proper way of doing that (starting from the sir name, to the name of the book then place and the year it was published) was also provided in the coursepack. Footnotes should not be confused with the end notes, we can take the help of Zotero here for the citing of footnotes and bibliographical references. It has refreshed my memory of mentioning the citations properly. EUCLID, however, advises against too much use of the quotes citing as it loses the originality of the work

It is worth mentioning that if the quote is more than four lines than it should be written in a separate paragraph with no quotation marks and with different (italic)font style.

Different examples of paraphrasing were also provided in the EUCLID coursepack which are really helpful in learning.

Another important rule to keep in mind while writing an essay is to give importance to the grammar and punctuations. In the coursepack of period one of EUCLID academic

and professional paper writing much emphasis has been given on the proper use of commas, semi colon and colon. Comma generally is used to join two independent clauses. Semi colon is used to join the two independent sentence. If the second sentence is dependent on first sentence, we cannot use semi colon. Instead a comma or full stop are used. For example: she loves playing guitar; it makes her forget about everything else going around.

Other than these the minute and proper details provided in coursepack of using apostrophe `s` in it's and its, and your and you're are quite beneficial for the student.

4) STYLE GUIDE

EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) (EUCLID 2015, 52) which is widely accepted style of references. Webster's Third New International Dictionary and Merriam- Webster's Collegiate Dictionary are the two dictionaries which can be preferably used by EUCLID's students.'

More often, in a single piece of writing we keep using both British and US style of writing without realizing the difference. In Pakistan, throughout our academic life we follow British way of writing, but now as a part of globalized world I have adopted the American way of writing. For example, the spellings of 'colour' has changed to 'color' (EUCLID 2015, 54). But at the same time while citing the quote I use full stop after quotation marks which is the British way of writing. In order to avoid the vagueness in terms of punctuations and vocabulary it is thus important to follow any particular style of writing.

Style guide part is important to me as I am keen in writing the op-eds in my future for the International newspapers. It gives us guidelines for the use of symbols, voice preferences (active vs passive) and the preferred length of the sentences (EUCLID 2015, 52). Few writers often criticize style guide as they believe that they have in born talent of creative writing. It, however, is important to know that in order to provide correct data in formal official and academic writings it is very important to follow the certain rules.

Capitalization rules are also clearly mentioned in EUCLID's coursepack. Three types of capitalization are used: full caps, heading caps and sentence caps. (EUCLID 2015, 66). Full caps are used in major headlines with each word of every character in full caps; heading caps and major caps on the other hand capitalize the first character but they don't capitalize the articles: a, and the. Prepositions: against, between, in, of, Conjunctions: and, but, for, nor, so, yet; and infinitive: to. Heading caps capitalizes the first and last words and all nouns, pronouns, adjectives and subordinating conjunctions.

It was refreshing to my knowledge that whenever the acronym is used first time in the sentence it should be introduced properly (EUCLID 2015, 66). For example, SAARC (South Asian Association of Regional Countries) conference was held last summer. It was agreed by all the SAARC participating countries that all issues must be resolved through mutual consensus.

In order to highlights the new word within the sentence and long quotations it is advised to use Italic font in the sentence. It should, however, be done only once and we should avoid using too much of it.

5) **ABBREVIATIONS**

The course ended with the number of Latin abbreviations used in informal writing and in footnotes and references. Formal way of writing like academic or official uses the English equivalent of Latin abbreviations. It is important to note that following this rule helps avoiding confusion in formal way of writing. Some of the examples mentioned in coursepack are: N.B which means ‘note well’ in English and ‘nota bene’ in Latin; ‘et al.,’ ‘et alii’ in Latin and, ‘and other people’ in English.

6) **CONCLUSION**

Before starting a master’s course, it is very important to refresh the academic and professional way of writing. In-text citations, references, paraphrasing use of hyphens and use of proper grammar will help me in my future writings. There are so many rules which are new to my knowledge. It is difficult to write all the specifics here provided by the EUCLID and the refresher course it gave. I owe EUCLID a lot for giving its students an opportunity to be a good writer by introducing this course and its details to its students. I’m very much looking forward to the next periods of this courses so that I can dive into the knowledge provided and learn more about this course.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1. Washington DC: EUCLID University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-perid-1>

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.